

Minimal Information Standards (MIS)

With the rise of open science and related initiatives, it is becoming increasingly feasible to conduct cross-analyses using data from repositories and archives—representing a major opportunity for scientific research. However, with greater capability comes greater responsibility: researchers must ensure that their own data are fully documented, transparent, reproducible, and suitable for integration into structured databases.

To support this, metadata standards have been established, and for high-throughput data in particular, so-called Minimal Information Standards (MIS) have been developed.

Key areas of MIS

Numerous standards and guidelines exist, and a well-designed standard typically addresses three key areas:

- specifications for file formats
- the metadata required to capture, present, and interpret the data and
- machine readability

The latter requires that data have a globally unambiguous semantic meaning. In addition, the provenance of the data—such as hardware components, settings, and measurement parameters—must be clearly documented.

Metadata used for quality control indicate whether data and measurement results are accurate, consistent, and complete.

The selected minimal information and metadata standards, as well as their specific implementation within a research group, can be documented in a data management plan (DMP), turning it into a living document.

Minimal Information Standards were specifically developed for high-throughput methods commonly used in the natural sciences (e.g., genomics, proteomics, and neuroscience). Since each field has different requirements for adequate documentation, a wide variety of such standards exists.

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